

“Pastores de Galicia”, guarantee of an artisan breeding way

Lamb and kid of Galician pastures, quality and sustainability.

THE WHAT AND WHY

The healthiest diet with the most natural meat

The “Pastores de Galicia” brand was created by the Association of Sheep and Goats Breeders of Galicia in 2015. Its objective is to distinguish in the market the lamb and goat meat produced in Galicia and associated with the use of natural resources by grazing mothers and feeding lambs and kids based on breast milk directly from the udder and cereals.

The “Pastores de Galicia” brand serves as a guarantee of origin, production system, food safety, animal welfare and quality. The current challenge is to publicize brand and product as well as its position in market in order to allow consumers to have access to a high-quality guaranteed meat. Meat from this extensive production system has excellent nutritional & organoleptic qualities.

Animals are linked to a sustainable breeding system at environmental level. Extensive livestock grazing systems based on fresh pastures are an active part of the environment in which it is located. These systems provide protection against forest fires while fertilize the soils in a natural form, among other benefits.

The Association of Sheep and Goats Breeders of Galicia is currently facing a divide between the food consumer and the origin of food. However, it has been detected a new tendency of consumers worrying about the sustainability and the quality of the food they consume. “Pastores de Galicia” allows to connect the security, quality and sustainability of the territory with the guarantee of a product of exceptional qualities for the final consumer.

Mixed flock grazing in a typical Galician pasture linked to silvopasture. Association of sheep and goats breeders of Galicia

Lamb cutting of the “Pastores de Galicia” brand at the gastronomic Forum of A Coruña 2019. Association of sheep and goats breeders of Galicia

HOW IS THE CHALLENGE ADDRESSED

The offer of a guaranteed quality meat

The innovation of the “Pastores de Galicia” brand lies in the connection that it achieves between the current consumption system and the traditional mode of production based on silvopastoral systems with shrub and herbaceous pastures. “Pastores de Galicia” allows the current consumer, physically detached from the rural environment, unaware of the value chain processing and production methods from the farm to the supermarket, be aware of these processes and link them with their growing awareness about environment and sustainable consumption providing access to a guaranteed lamb meat that comes from sustainable

farming systems that respect natural conditions of animals and environment. Reaching consumer is key to connect consumer distribution points with production ones. “Pastores de Galicia” brand, the Association of Sheep and Goats Breeders of Galicia, boosts marketing campaigns, product promotions and working to publicise what is behind the label. It is essential that distributors commit themselves to this type of product and its characteristics and accept the challenge of offering more quality, less homogeneity fair prices.

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HIGHLIGHTS

The sustainable breeding aims to approach the demanding consumer in terms of quality and environmentally friendly productions.

It is important to reach the consumer directly with a brand that protects the quality of a craft product.

The "Pastores de Galicia" brand guarantees a meat of high nutritional and organoleptic values produced in a sustainable way within the framework of agroforestry systems.

Farmers in extensive collaborate in the care and protection of nature.

Lamb dish made with Pastores de Galicia product. Association of sheep and goats breeders of Galicia.

FURTHER INFORMATION

www.ovica.org

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=JuxGmTY_B0w

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ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES

The difficulty of creating something different and of excellent result

Recovering the way of breeding lambs and kinds of livestock breeds in risk of extinction is a challenge for all farmers who venture. The current economic system is not yet aimed at favoring the sustainable producer, local systems and achieving high quality rather than high productivity. Facing this difficulty, the Association of Sheep and Goats Breeders of Galicia have farmers who are aware of the change in the production model, willing to wage another way of doing things and in turn budding policies that are increasingly valuing sustainable systems and agroecology, included Agroforestry.

The extensive model has great facilities to start the activity in Galicia, where a large amount of high-quality land is available and suitable for grazing. The investment in the farm itself is not high because the establishment of the needed infrastructures is minimal.

Farmer has always been the last to collect his share of the work, most of benefits are staying along the way, in logistics and distributors. With our brand "Pastores de Galicia", the Association of Sheep and Goats Breeders of Galicia manage to shorten distances between producer and consumer, the Association of Sheep and Goats Breeders of Galicia group farmers to facilitate sales and therefore promote farmer receive a greater portion of the economic distribution derived from his work.

The product that results from this breeding system following an extensive model has the characteristic of not being homogeneous in terms of size, and sometimes not in terms of taste, which is a difficulty. Moreover, the quality is less and less associated with the concept of homogeneity, and it is necessary to transfer this issue to the population. It is an inconvenience that still homogeneity and quality are so linked. This makes it difficult to incorporate our product through large supermarkets that still request high homogeneous size product. The advantage is that the consumer is changing, is increasingly informed and begins to believe in other quality formats.

The media today is available to all companies, brands and most consumers make inquiries via internet to find new products. This is an advantage, since it is feasible to reach a high number of potential consumers to publicize the "Pastores de Galicia" brand, without the need to make large advertising investments.

Internet sales are another favorable tool for our project, since it allows us to shorten sale channels, which will become an almost direct system between producer and final consumer.

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